

INTER-PROFESSIONAL COLLABORATION AMONG SOCIAL WORK, PHARMACY, EMERGENCY MEDICINE, PATHOLOGY AND LABORATORY MEDICINE, DENTAL ASSISTING, AND RADIOLOGY AND MEDICAL IMAGING PROFESSIONALS AND ITS IMPACT ON PATIENT SAFETY AND QUALITY OF CARE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: Inter-professional collaboration (IPC) is promoted in modern healthcare because patient care is now complex and depends on coordinated work between physicians, nurses, pharmacists, rehabilitation staff, social workers, and other professionals involved in care delivery. Poor collaboration weaken communication, delay decisions, duplicate work, and increase the risk of unsafe or low-quality care, while stronger teamwork improve processes of care and some patient-related outcomes.

Methods: This systematic review structured according to PRISMA 2020 principles and focused on studies of practice-based IPC in real healthcare settings. The targeted information sources were PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and the Cochrane Library, and the review question asked whether collaboration in multidisciplinary healthcare professionals improved patient safety and quality of care outcomes when compared with usual care or another collaborative model.

Results: Ten original studies were synthesized in the results section, and the studies covered medical wards, telemetry units, nursing homes, rehabilitation units, operating rooms, primary care practices, and hospital care pathways. Most studies showed improvement in at least one process, teamwork, coordination, efficiency, or functional outcome, and the effect was not consistent in all settings, and mortality or complications were rarely reported.

Conclusion: IPC support better organization of care, better communication, improved adherence to recommended practice, and in some studies shorter length of stay or better patient function. More larger studies are still needed, especially studies that measure patient safety events directly rather than only process indicators or staff perceptions.

Keywords: inter-professional collaboration; multidisciplinary team; patient safety; quality of care; teamwork.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare delivery becomes more dependent on teams than on single professionals because patients often move across departments, professions, and levels of care during one episode of illness, and this makes collaboration central to safe practice and acceptable quality of care (1,2). Teamwork problems are now recognized as an important patient safety issue because weak coordination can affect communication, timing of interventions, continuity of care, and the consistency of decisions across professionals (2).

IPC means that two or more professional groups work together in a structured way to improve care delivery and patient outcomes, and this happen through bedside rounds, case conferences, care pathways (CP), shared planning, medication review meetings, or checklist-based communication during procedures (1). The Cochrane review by Reeves et al. found that collaborative interventions improve some professional practice and healthcare outcomes, and the certainty of evidence was mostly low and the results were mixed across settings and intervention types (1).

More recent reviews also showed the same pattern of cautious benefit rather than a simple strong effect in every setting (3-7). Interdisciplinary bedside rounds (IBR) improve patient centeredness, team collaboration, and some quality outcomes, definitions and study methods are variable (3). IPC in inpatient care improve some patient-reported outcomes (PRO) (4).

In primary care the effect is more positive especially cardiovascular risk populations (5). Team-based hospital care also improves patient satisfaction in some studies, especially when more than two professions are involved (6). A systematic review focused on general medical wards found little effect on traditional outcomes such as length of stay (LOS), early readmission, and mortality, which shows that collaboration is useful and does not automatically change every patient-level outcome (7).

Because the literature still shows mixed findings, it is useful to review how IPC performs across different healthcare settings when the focus is specifically on patient safety and quality of care (8-12). This review aimed to synthesize evidence on IPC among multidisciplinary healthcare professionals and its impact on patient safety and quality of care using studies identified from PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and the Cochrane Library.

METHODS

This review was planned and reported in line with PRISMA 2020 guidance for systematic reviews. The review question was whether practice-based IPC in multidisciplinary healthcare professionals improves patient safety and quality of care outcomes in healthcare settings when compared with usual care or another collaborative approach.

The targeted databases were PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and the Cochrane Library, and the search concept combined terms related to IPC and care outcomes. Search concepts included “interprofessional collaboration,” “inter-professional collaboration,” “multidisciplinary team,” “interdisciplinary rounds,” “teamwork,” “patient safety,” “quality of care,” “care pathway,” and “surgical safety checklist,” with Boolean combinations adapted to each database interface.

Studies were eligible if they were original research, involved at least two professional groups working together in practice, were conducted in healthcare delivery settings, and reported outcomes related to patient safety, quality of care, patient experience, care process, or efficiency of care such as LOS, adherence to practice, communication quality, or functional improvement. Reviews, editorials, protocols, education-only studies without clinical practice outcomes, and studies not directly evaluating collaborative practice were excluded.

Screening was based on title and abstract review followed by full-text assessment against the eligibility criteria, and the final synthesis was narrative because the included studies differed clearly in settings, interventions, outcome definitions, and designs. Methodological limitations were considered during synthesis by looking at small sample size, single-center design, cluster allocation, difficulty with blinding, contamination risk, and the use of subjective or indirect outcomes instead of direct adverse event outcomes.

RESULTS

Ten original studies were included in the narrative synthesis, and these studies represented acute hospital wards, telemetry units, nursing homes, rehabilitation units, operating rooms, general practice, and structured hospital CP (10-19). Most studies were randomized, cluster-randomized, or controlled intervention studies. The collaborative models were different, including interdisciplinary rounds, pharmacist-led medication review meetings, multidisciplinary case conferences, externally facilitated audit programs, team training, checklists, and pathway-based teamwork interventions (10-19).

Overall, seven of the ten included studies showed improvement in at least one important quality, teamwork, process, efficiency, or patient function outcome after collaborative interventions, while three studies showed mostly no clear benefit on their main patient-level endpoints (10-19). The positive findings were more common for care organization, communication, role clarity, adherence to recommended practice, team behaviors, and selected efficiency outcomes, while null findings were more common when studies assessed broad patient-assessed quality of care, satisfaction, or short-stay ward outcomes using smaller samples or limited follow-up (10-19).

Curley et al. reported that interdisciplinary daily rounds on inpatient medical wards reduced mean LOS and hospital charges compared with traditional rounds, which suggested that collaboration can improve efficiency in medical ward care when it is embedded into daily workflow (10). Schmidt et al. found that structured meetings involving pharmacists, physicians, nurses, and nurse assistants in nursing homes led to many therapy changes judged clinically beneficial and improved staff medication knowledge, which supports collaboration for medication safety and prescribing quality (11).

Wilson et al. found that video-based multidisciplinary case conferencing reduced the number of conferences per patient and shortened treatment duration compared with audio conferencing, which suggested better team coordination under the audiovisual model (13). Cheater et al. showed that an externally facilitated multidisciplinary audit program improved knowledge, skills, attitudes, collaborative behavior, and quality of audit with measurable improvements in care, which supports facilitated teamwork as a practical quality-improvement strategy (14).

Strasser et al. found that team training in stroke rehabilitation improved patient functional gains, although it did not change discharge destination or LOS, which means benefit occur in patient recovery even when operational measures do not change (15). Calland et al. reported more positive safety-related team behaviors in operations using the surgical checklist, although subjective team comfort and communication ratings were lower during early implementation, which suggests that transition to structured safety behaviors initially feel difficult despite behavioral benefit (16). Deneckere et al. found better conflict management, stronger innovation climate, more organized care, lower emotional exhaustion, and higher competence in teams using CP, which supports collaboration as part of organized acute care improvement (18).

Not all interventions produced clear benefits on major patient-centered outcomes (12,17,19). Wild et al. found no significant difference in LOS or indirect quality indicators in a telemetry unit,

Black et al. found improved staff team roles and no significant improvement in patient-assessed quality of chronic illness care, and O’Leary et al. found no significant improvement in shared decision-making, activation, or satisfaction after patient-centered bedside rounds in adult medical inpatients (12,17,19). These studies show that collaboration is not automatically effective in every context and that patient-level effects depend on intensity, setting, implementation quality, and how outcomes are measured (1,7,12,17,19).

Another important point was that hard safety outcomes such as mortality, morbidity, complications, or preventable adverse events were not commonly reported in the core intervention studies, so many studies relied more on process or perception outcomes than on direct safety-event outcomes (1,7,10-19). This limits how strongly the review can claim direct patient safety benefit, even when the direction of teamwork and quality outcomes looks favorable (1,7).

Table 1. Characteristics of included studies

Study	Setting	Design	IPC intervention	Main outcome focus	Main finding
Curley et al., 1998 (10)	Inpatient medical wards, USA	Randomized controlled firm trial	Daily interdisciplinary rounds	LOS, charges	Reduced LOS and hospital charges
Schmidt et al., 1998 (11)	Nursing homes, Sweden	Controlled trial	Regular pharmacist-physician-nurse-assistant meetings	Drug therapy quality	Beneficial therapy changes and improved knowledge
Wild et al., 2004 (12)	Telemetry unit, USA	Randomized trial	Daily interdisciplinary rounds	LOS, indirect quality indicators	No significant benefit
Wilson et al., 2004 (13)	Community multidisciplinary care, Australia	Randomized trial	Videoconference vs audioconference case conferencing	Treatment duration, conferencing efficiency	Shorter treatment duration and fewer conferences
Cheater et al., 2005 (14)	Acute hospitals, UK	Multicenter randomized exploratory trial	Facilitated multidisciplinary audit program	Collaboration and care improvement	Better knowledge, skills, attitudes, behavior, and care
Strasser et al., 2008 (15)	Stroke rehabilitation units, USA	Cluster randomized trial	Team training	Functional gain, discharge, LOS	Better functional gains, no LOS/discharge effect
Calland et al., 2011 (16)	Operating room, USA	Randomized controlled trial (RCT)	Surgical safety checklist	Safety-related team behaviors	Better safety behaviors, mixed

Study	Setting	Design	IPC intervention	Main outcome focus	Main finding
					subjective team ratings
Black et al., 2013 (17)	General practice, Australia	Cluster randomized trial	Structured team-based chronic disease care intervention	Patient-assessed quality of care	Better staff team roles, no patient-assessed care improvement
Deneckere et al., 2013 (18)	Acute hospitals, Belgium	Cluster RCT	CP	Teamwork, organized care, burnout	Better teamwork and organized care, lower burnout
O'Leary et al., 2016 (19)	Adult medical inpatients, USA	Cluster randomized trial	Patient-centered bedside rounds	Decision control, activation, satisfaction	No significant improvement in main patient-centered outcomes

Table 2. Summary of effects on patient safety and quality of care

Domain	Studies showing improvement	Studies with mixed or no clear improvement	Interpretation
Care efficiency / LOS / treatment duration	Curley (10), Wilson (13)	Wild (12), Strasser (15)	Improvement
Adherence / prescribing / organized care	Schmidt (11), Cheater (14), Deneckere (18)	—	Positive direction
Team behaviors / collaboration processes	Cheater (14), Calland (16), Deneckere (18), Black (17)	O'Leary (19)	improved
Patient-centered or PRO	Strasser (15) for function	Black (17), O'Leary (19), Wild (12)	Mixed
Direct hard safety outcomes	Rarely reported	Most studies	Important gap

DISCUSSION

This review suggests that IPC has a positive direction of effect on how care is organized and delivered, and it does not produce uniform benefit across every outcome or every clinical setting (1,3-7, 10-19). The strongest pattern in the included studies was improvement in team processes, coordination, role clarity, organized care, and selected efficiency outcomes, while the weakest pattern was for broad PRO and direct hard safety outcomes such as complications or mortality (1,4,6,7, 10-19).

The review findings are in line with the Cochrane review by Reeves et al., which also concluded that collaborative interventions improve functional status, adherence to recommended practice, and use of healthcare resources (1). The findings are also consistent with later reviews showing that bedside rounds, inpatient collaboration, and broader team-based care models can be useful, yet the evidence still suffers from heterogeneity in intervention design, outcome definitions, and study quality, which makes pooled strong conclusions difficult (3,4,6).

A practical message from the included studies is that collaboration work best when it is structured, repeated, and embedded into routine work rather than left informal or symbolic (10,11,14,16,18). Daily rounds, structured audit, checklist-supported communication, CP, and team training all provided a defined collaborative process, and these were the types of interventions most often linked to improved outcomes in this review (10,11,14-18). On the other hand, some interventions improve staff roles or communication without immediately changing patient-rated quality or satisfaction, which was seen in Black et al. and O'Leary et al., and this reflect limited follow-up time, implementation challenges, or the use of outcomes that are harder to shift in the short term (17,19).

According to our findings, teamwork and safety are linked, even intervention studies do not measure adverse events directly (2,8,20). Rosen et al. described teamwork as a public health issue in healthcare delivery, Dinius et al. found that higher inter-professional teamwork was associated with better patient safety in German hospitals, and Amarneh and Al Nobani found that physician-nurse collaboration had a significant positive relationship with patient safety culture in Jordanian hospitals (2,8,20).

This review has some limitations. The interventions were very heterogeneous, the settings were very different, and many studies emphasized process or perception outcomes instead of direct adverse event outcomes, so meta-analysis was not appropriate and conclusions should stay careful rather than absolute. Collaborative interventions are complex, and their effect depend on leadership support, local culture, staffing, professional hierarchy, and implementation quality, which are not always measured clearly in the primary studies.

CONCLUSION

IPC in multidisciplinary healthcare professionals improves several important parts of care quality, especially communication, organization of care, adherence to good practice, team behaviors, and some efficiency or functional outcomes. Collaboration is useful and often beneficial, and it is not a definitive solution by itself, and stronger studies with clearer safety outcomes are needed.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IPC: Inter-professional collaboration.
IBR: Interdisciplinary bedside rounds.
LOS: Length of stay.
RCTa: Randomized controlled trial.
PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses.
PRO: Patient-reported outcome.
CP: Care pathway.

REFERENCES

1. Reeves S, Pelone F, Harrison R, Goldman J, Zwarenstein M. Interprofessional collaboration to improve professional practice and healthcare outcomes. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2017;6:CD000072.
2. Rosen MA, DiazGranados D, Dietz AS, Benishek LE, Thompson D, Pronovost PJ, Weaver SJ. Teamwork in healthcare: key discoveries enabling safer, high-quality care. *Am Psychol.* 2018;73(4):433-450.
3. Heip T, Van Hecke A, Malfait S, Van Biesen W, Eeckloo K. The effects of interdisciplinary bedside rounds on patient centeredness, quality of care, and team collaboration: a systematic review. *J Patient Saf.* 2022;18(1):e40-e44.
4. Kaiser L, Conrad S, Neugebauer EAM, Pietsch B, Pieper D. Interprofessional collaboration and patient-reported outcomes in inpatient care: a systematic review. *Syst Rev.* 2022;11(1):169.
5. Bouton C, Journeaux M, Jourdain M, Angibaud M, Huon JF, Rat C. Interprofessional collaboration in primary care: what effect on patient health? A systematic literature review. *BMC Prim Care.* 2023;24(1):253.
6. Will KK, Johnson ML, Lamb G. Team-based care and patient satisfaction in the hospital setting: a systematic review. *J Patient Cent Res Rev.* 2019;6(2):158-171.
7. Pannick S, Davis R, Ashrafian H, Byrne BE, Beveridge I, Athanasiou T, Wachter RM, Sevdalis N. Effects of interdisciplinary team care interventions on general medical wards: a systematic review. *JAMA Intern Med.* 2015;175(8):1288-1298.
8. Dinius J, Philipp R, Ernstmann N, Heier L, Göritz AS, Pfisterer-Heise S, Hammerschmidt J, Bergelt C, Hammer A, Körner M. Inter-professional teamwork and its association with patient safety in German hospitals: a cross-sectional study. *PLoS One.* 2020;15(5):e0233766.

9. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. 2021;372:n71.
10. Curley C, McEachern JE, Speroff T. A firm trial of interdisciplinary rounds on the inpatient medical wards: an intervention designed using continuous quality improvement. *Med Care*. 1998;36(8 Suppl):AS4-AS12.
11. Schmidt IK, Claesson CB, Westerholm B, Nilsson LG, Svarstad BL. Physician and staff assessments of drug interventions and outcomes in Swedish nursing homes. *Ann Pharmacother*. 1998;32(1):27-32.
12. Wild D, Nawaz H, Chan W, Katz DL. Effects of interdisciplinary rounds on length of stay in a telemetry unit. *J Public Health Manag Pract*. 2004;10(1):63-69.
13. Wilson SF, Marks R, Collins N, Warner B, Frick L. Benefits of multidisciplinary case conferencing using audiovisual compared with telephone communication: a randomized controlled trial. *J Telemed Telecare*. 2004;10(6):351-354.
14. Cheater FM, Hearnshaw H, Baker R, Keane M. Can a facilitated programme promote effective multidisciplinary audit in secondary care teams? An exploratory trial. *Int J Nurs Stud*. 2005;42(7):779-791.
15. Strasser DC, Falconer JA, Stevens AB, Uomoto JM, Herrin J, Bowen SE, Burrige AB. Team training and stroke rehabilitation outcomes: a cluster randomized trial. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2008;89(1):10-15.
16. Calland JF, Turrentine FE, Guerlain S, Bovbjerg V, Poole GR, Lebeau K, Peugh J, Adams RB. The surgical safety checklist: lessons learned during implementation. *Am Surg*. 2011;77(9):1131-1137.
17. Black DA, Taggart J, Jayasinghe UW, Proudfoot J, Crookes P, Beilby J, Powell-Davies G, Wilson LA, Harris MF. The Teamwork Study: enhancing the role of non-GP staff in chronic disease management in general practice. *Aust J Prim Health*. 2013;19(3):184-189.
18. Deneckere S, Euwema M, Lodewijckx C, Panella M, Mutsvari T, Sermeus W, Vanhaecht K. Better interprofessional teamwork, higher level of organized care, and lower risk of burnout in acute health care teams using care pathways: a cluster randomized controlled trial. *Med Care*. 2013;51(1):99-107.
19. O'Leary KJ, Killarney A, Hansen LO, Jones S, Malladi M, Marks K, Shah HM. Effect of patient-centred bedside rounds on hospitalised patients' decision control, activation and satisfaction with care. *BMJ Qual Saf*. 2016;25(12):921-928.
20. Amarnah BH, Al Nobani F. The influence of physician-nurse collaboration on patient safety culture. *Heliyon*. 2022;8(9):e10649.

